

Determining the Practice Level of Occupational Health and Safety Measures at a Construction Site

Ibrahim Halil Geçibesler, Tuncay Şaşar

¹ Department of Occupational Health and Safety, Faculty of Health Sciences, University of Bingöl, 12000 Bingöl, Türkiye, Email: igeibesler@bingol.edu.tr., ORCID: 0000-0002-4473-2671, ² Department of Occupational Health and Safety, Institute of Science, University of Bingöl, 12000 Bingöl, Türkiye

Abstract: This research was conducted to determine the practice level of occupational health and safety (OHS) measures based on the socio-demographic and occupational characteristics and views on OHS practices of construction site employees. A personal information form was used as a data collection tool to reveal the socio-demographic and occupational characteristics of the employees. Additionally, a scale for employees' views on the OHS practices was used to determine the practice level of OHS measures. The expressions in the scale reflected the OHS perception of the employees, as well as their satisfaction, perception of responsibility and obligation, OHS training status, employees' views on the OHS responsibility of the managers, employees' views on OHS practices of the occupational safety experts, and employees' views on the OHS attitudes of the construction site managers. The significance levels of the relationships between the socio-demographic and occupational characteristics of the employees and their views on OHS practices were determined with Spearman correlation analysis, Mann-Whitney U, Kruskal-Wallis H, and multiple comparison tests. The study results may be used as an important guide to be used in construction sites that are famous for fatal work accidents, difficult working conditions and unsafe environments, as well as a tool to provide important data to construction site studies.

Keywords: Occupational health and safety, construction site, OHS perception, employees' views, OHS practices.

Determinar o nível de prática das medidas de saúde e segurança ocupacional numa obra de construção

Resumo: Esta pesquisa foi realizada para determinar o nível de prática de medidas de saúde e segurança no trabalho (SST) com base nas características sociodemográficas e ocupacionais e nas opiniões sobre as práticas de SST dos funcionários de obra de construção. Foi utilizado um inquérito de informações pessoais como instrumento de coleta de dados para revelar as características sociodemográficas e ocupacionais dos funcionários. Além disso, foi utilizada uma escala de opiniões dos funcionários sobre as práticas de SST para determinar o nível de concretização das medidas de SST. As expressões da escala procuraram registar a percepção de SST dos funcionários, bem como sua satisfação, percepção de responsabilidade e obrigação, status de formação de SST, opiniões dos funcionários sobre a responsabilidade de SST dos gerentes, opiniões dos funcionários sobre as práticas de SST dos técnicos de segurança, e opiniões dos funcionários sobre as atitudes de SST dos gestores da obra de construção. Os níveis de significância das relações entre as características sociodemográficas e ocupacionais dos funcionários e suas opiniões sobre as práticas de SST foram determinados com análise de Correlação de Spearman, Mann-Whitney U, Kruskal-Wallis H e testes de comparação múltipla. Os resultados do estudo podem ser utilizados como um guia importante para uso em estaleiros de obras famosos por acidentes de trabalho fatais, condições de trabalho difíceis e ambientes inseguros, bem como uma ferramenta para fornecer dados importantes para estudos de obras de construção.

Palavras-chave: Saúde e segurança ocupacional, obra de construção, percepção de SST, visão dos funcionários, práticas de SST.

1. Introduction

Construction sites are exposed to natural environmental factors that can be harmful to health, such as dust, high noise levels, inadequate lighting, and intensive work with hazardous chemicals, working at heights, using heavy equipment, lifting heavy materials, and working in crowded environments. This makes construction sites one of the most hazardous industries (Vitharana et al., 2015; Dong et al., 2015). Furthermore, the lack of training, long working hours, intense workload, low wages, poor team performance, and the use of unsafe equipment cause stress in construction site employees. These stress factors negatively affect productivity, job satisfaction, and employee motivation, and can lead to occupational accidents and diseases due to unsafe situations and actions by employees (Demirkesen & Arditi; 2015; Kikuchi et al., 2020). One of the most common work accidents that occur on construction sites is the death of an employee as a result of falling from a height. For this reason, the Occupational Safety and Health Organization (OSHA) in the USA has made fall protection systems mandatory in areas where work is done at heights higher than 1.82 m (OSHA, 2018). Fall protection systems such as safety nets, guardrails, and personal fall arrest systems can be utilized on construction sites to prevent falls and ensure the safety of employees.

Construction site employees mostly perform manual work or use equipment, leading to inevitable occupational accidents due to unsafe behavior. Studies have shown that 80% of accidents on construction sites are due to unsafe behavior of employees, while illnesses are mainly caused by working in incorrect postures and not using personal protective equipment (Duan & Zhou, 2023). Implementing behavior-based safety training is crucial in preventing these work accidents and occupational disease. Training that addresses employee behavior and responsibility perception can effectively eliminate unsafe behaviors. Factors that contribute to unsafe behavior include inadequate safety management, pressure to meet production targets, lack of training, competitive work environment, tight construction schedules, and limited resources. Another important factor that has an important impact on employees' unsafe behavior is manager attitudes. Moreover, studies indicate that unsafe situations and actions at construction sites are related to manager behaviors (Fang & Wu, 2013; Wang et al., 2016). Additionally, reasons for fatal accidents include falls, slips, being struck by objects, electric shocks, and being caught between objects (Li et al., 2015; Yi & Chan, 2016; Jaafar et al., 2018). Encouraging employees to prioritize safety measures and use proper personal protective equipment can help reduce the number of fatal work accidents and illnesses.

For perfect OHS practices at construction sites, meaning zero work accidents and occupational disease-based OHS practices, organizations, managers, OHS professionals, and special-duty employees must work together to determine the hazards at the construction site with a holistic approach and create risk maps that will develop depending on the hazards. During construction site work, employees' behavior is monitored and their expectations are recorded as feedback. Goals such as specifying preventive measures, determining priorities, organization, manager/responsible behavior, use of appropriate personal protection, OHS inspections, professional qualification certificate, and complete mechanical safety equipment and training activities are important and vital goals to achieve the aim of perfect OHS practices at construction sites. Questioning, analyzing, implementing, and producing highly efficient solution suggestions for the difficulties in the practice of each target will contribute to the success of the target. There is a significant relationship between the goals set and implemented in construction site environments and

performance. Because the targets are created under the umbrella of systematic knowledge to achieve a specific OHS goal, the performance of employees/responsible people/managers will affect the success of the targets. If the targets are not achieved, perfect OHS practices will not work.

Therefore, the flawless implementation of the above-mentioned OHS practices in construction sites, which are very dangerous and unsafe environments, is limited to the efforts of the employees. In this context, the study includes comparing the OHS views of labor-intensive construction site employees with their socio-demographic and occupational characteristics. The research study examined the practice of OHS measures in high-risk construction sites with fatal work accidents caused by unsafe actions of employees. It explored the relationship between employees' OHS views, socio-demographic factors, and occupational characteristics. The study resulted in an important practical guide that conveys employees' views to managers and OHS professionals when explaining the OHS measures to be practiced at construction sites and in risk assessment studies. It should definitely not be forgotten that in OHS studies, exemplary OHS practices operating in the same sector should be taken into account to ensure zero work accidents and occupational diseases.

2. Theoretical background

2.1. Accident Models and Risk factors

In the past, "theoretical accident models" were used to explain the risk factors that cause general work accidents and occupational diseases. Later, "accident causality models" specific to construction sites were developed. Theoretical accident models include: "Goals Freedom Alertness Theory" (Kerr, 1957; Heinrich, 1969), "Domino theory", "Multiple causation" (Petersen, 1971), "Updated domino sequence" (Bird, 1974), "Ferrel Theory" (Heinrich, 1980), "the Swiss Cheese model of human error" (Reason, 2000) and "Human Factor Analysis and Classification System" (Shappell & Wiegmann, 1997). Accident causality models include: "Accident Root Causes Tracing Model" (Abdelhamid & Everett, 2000), "Constraint-response Model" (Suraji et al., 2001), "Modified Loss Causation Model" (Chua & Goh, 2004), "Descriptive Accident Causation Model" (Mitropoulos et al., 2005), and "Human Error Awareness Training" (Garrett & Teizer, 2009). Both models highlight common risk factors such as organizational culture, supervisory influences, preconditions, management system, employees' unsafe acts, psychological work environment, unsafe conditions, employees' improper response to unsafe conditions, proximity and distance factors, safety efforts to control conditions, and task unpredictability. When these risk factors are taken into account as leading indicators of work accidents and occupational diseases, expanding the OHS awareness of construction site employees can contribute to the practice of corrective OHS activities and the development of preventive measures on construction sites.

2.2. Safety Culture and Safety Climate

In terms of OHS practices, safety culture has been explained using three different approaches. The first approach is based on scientific, anthropological, and emergent principles in work environments, both in the past and today. The second approach is based on analytical, pragmatic, and daily attitude principles in working environments. Finally, the third approach is based on normative, pragmatic, and organizational principles in work environments (Silbey, 2009; Guldenmund, 2010; Edwards et al., 2013). To study

safety culture in general working environments and construction sites, a combination of three approaches is utilized. This includes the use of qualitative and quantitative measurement methods, management styles, and survey techniques to gather information about the safety culture of businesses.

General and holistic methods to eliminate the situations that lead to occupational risks in construction sites have been applied in "Behavior-Based Safety". "Theory of Planned Behavior," and "Leadership-Culture-Behavior" working environments (Ajzen, 1991; Cox et al., 2004; Fang et al., 2020). In line with these methods and the suggestions of other researchers (Zohar & Luria, 2005, Fang & Wu, 2013), positive applications of factors such as monitoring and control, promoting learning, safety climate, safety culture, proactive management practices, and relationships between stakeholders, as well as communication between employees and managers, make positive contributions to the OHS management system at the construction site.

According to the theory of planned behavior, aims create sub-goals. Determining and implementing sub-goals requires a perfect organization and its operation. The OHS responsibilities of the employees/managers in the organization and its operation at the construction site create an OHS perception among the employees, which is expressed by the safety climate. A strong safety climate created by senior managers or OHS professionals at construction sites will prevent occupational accidents and diseases at construction sites. Each OHS parameter applied in the safety climate created at construction sites, which creates a perception among employees, also reflects the responsibility of the organization. In this context, survey research based on the theory of planned behavior at construction sites provides information about the behaviors of the organization/managers/OHS professionals/employees depending on both internal and external factors.

3. Materials and Methods

3.1. Research Hypotheses

The safety triangle model representation of the empirical study designed with hypotheses to determine the practice level of OSH measures at construction sites is shown in Figure 1. In the model, "safe working" is achieved through OSH measures, positive socio-demographic and occupational characteristics of employees, and their acceptance of OHS practices. Otherwise, it results in "unsafe working". In studies on occupational safety in the literature, there is a strong correlation between employees' age and their performance, work strength, and mobility. As employees age, negative changes can occur in their thinking, perception, and reactions, which can have a detrimental impact on productivity and safe behavior. However, it has been observed that married employees with children tend to act more cautiously in the workplace, reflecting their sense of responsibility (Amegayibor, 2021). This can influence employees' perceptions of OHS in the workplace. In fact, a study found that employees in higher and more responsible positions were less likely to experience work accidents due to their experience and success (Jafari et al., 2019). While improvements in work and working conditions are important in reducing occupational accidents, the main factor is often the lack of education and unconscious actions of employees, as accidents are mostly human-related and caused by lack of training (Flegl et al., 2022).

- Based on these explanations, the following hypotheses were tested in the research:
- Hypothesis 1 (H1): There is a significant relationship between the practice level of OHS measures and employees' age (EA).
 - Hypothesis 2 (H2): There is a significant relationship between the practice level of OHS measures and occupational experience (OE).
 - Hypothesis 3 (H3): There is a significant relationship between the practice level of OHS measures and daily working time (DWT).
 - Hypothesis 4 (H4): There is a significant difference between the practice level of OHS measures and marital status (MS).
 - Hypothesis 5 (H5): There is a significant difference between the practice level of OHS measures and employees' occupation (EO).
 - Hypothesis 6 (H6): There is a significant difference between the practice level of OHS measures and education level (EL).
 - Hypothesis 7 (H7): There is a significant difference between the practice level of OHS measures and monthly income (MI).
 - Hypothesis 8 (H8): There is a significant difference between the practice level of OHS measures and job satisfaction (JS).
 - Hypothesis 9 (H9): There is a significant difference between the practice level of OHS measures and sleepovers at work (SW).
 - Hypothesis 10 (H10): There is a significant difference between the practice level of OHS measures and working at height (WH).
 - Hypothesis 11 (H11): There is a significant difference between the practice level of OHS measures and had professional qualification certificate (PQC).
 - Hypothesis 12 (H12): There is a significant difference between the practice level of OHS measures and received training on working at height (TWH).
 - Hypothesis 13 (H13): There is a significant difference between the practice level of OHS measures and received OHS training (TOHS).

Figure 1: The proposed safety triangle model for testing the empirical study with hypotheses

3.2. Research Model

The research utilized a descriptive scanning model to test the proposed hypotheses. Scanning models are created using a large set of data, either from the entire universe or a subset of it. The descriptive model aims to define and explain various events, objects, entities, institutions, groups, and fields (Calışkan & Kılınc, 2012). This research model involves observing, recording, discovering relationships between events, and generalizing unchanging control principles. In essence, the descriptive function of science is emphasized (De Barros et al., 2018).

3.3. Data Collection Tools and Analysis

The study population consists of 200 employees who are employed at a construction site in Bingöl, a province of Türkiye. The sample includes 132 employees who were selected through simple random sampling at the construction site. This study utilized a two-part survey to collect data. The first part included questions about socio-demographic and occupational information, work-related factors, job satisfaction, and safety training. The second part focused on attitudes and perceptions related to OHS. The reliability of the obtained data was assessed using Cronbach's Alpha coefficient. Additionally, the normal distribution suitability of the data was determined using Kolmogorov-Smirnov values (Table1).

It was noted that a p -value of less than 0.05 indicated non-normal distribution (Song & Zhao, 2021). Therefore, non-parametric test methods were utilized in the research. The Mann-Whitney U test was employed to evaluate OHS measures and compare binary variable groups, while the Kruskal-Wallis H test was used to compare more than two variable groups. The Tukey multiple comparison test method was utilized to determine the source of the difference. For the current study, an ethics committee permission report with document date and number (21/10/2020-E.19399) was received from Bingöl University Scientific Research and Publication Ethics Committee.

Table 1. Normality test results

	Kolmogorov-Smirnov		
	Statistics	Frequency	Significance (p -value)
Satisfaction level of employees	0.083	132	0.026
Employees' perception of responsibility	0.218	132	0.000
Employees' perception of obligation	0.200	132	0.000
OHS educational status of employees	0.140	132	0.000
OHS perceptions of employees	0.114	132	0.000
Employees' views on OHS responsibilities of managers	0.167	132	0.000
Employees' views on OHS practices of occupational safety experts	0.105	132	0.001
Employees' views on OHS attitude of construction site managers	0.182	132	0.000

4. Results and Discussions

4.1. Socio-demographic and occupational characteristics and views on OHS of employees

The research findings revealed that the average age of the employees was 33.9 ± 9.3 , with an average occupational experience of 11.2 ± 6.4 years and an average daily

working hours of 8.7 ± 1.1 . Furthermore, the study found that 72.7% of the employees were married, while 27.3% were single (Table 2).

Table 2. Averages of age, occupation experience and daily working time in construction site employees and their marital status

	Age	Occupation experience	Daily working hours
Mean±sd	33.9 ± 9.3	11.2 ± 6.4	8.7 ± 1.1
	Marital status		
	Married		Single
Frequency	96		36
Percentage (%)	72.7		27.3

As shown in Figure 2 (a), the distribution of construction site employees according to occupation groups was bricklayer (40.9%), ironsmith (18.2%), plasterer (15.2%), moulder (12.9%), and other occupation groups (12.9%). The educational status of the employees consisted of primary school (31.8%), primary education (28.8%), high school (19.7%), illiterate (12.1%), and bachelor's degree (7.6%), as shown in Figure 2b. The majority of the employees were moulders, with their education level consisting of primary school (5 years) and primary education (5 years) graduates. Monthly incomes of employees ranged from \$800 to \$1200 and above, but the majority (57.6%) earned \$800, while a small portion (3.0%) earned over \$1200 (Figure 2c). As can be seen in Figure 2 (d), an attempt was made to learn the OHS backgrounds of the employees by asking questions about OHS practices to the construction site employees. In this context, in response to the question “have you ever had a work accident before?”, only 4.5% of the employees stated that they had a work accident and the others did not. In response to the question “Do your sleepover at the workplace?” 34.8% of employees answered yes.

Figure 2: Distribution of construction site employees according to their occupational groups (a), distribution of their education levels (b), distribution of their monthly income (c), yes-no rates in which they answered questions about their OHS backgrounds (d).

In follow-up questions, 63.3% of the employees stated that they received training on working at height. Additionally, 77.3% of construction site employees stated that their occupation requires working at heights. The majority of employees (78.8%) stated that they were satisfied with their work. Risk factors such as heavy workload, negative working environments and poor working conditions (Goetz et al., 2013) may be caused the dissatisfaction of 21.2% of the construction site employees. The rate of employees receiving OHS training was quite high (80.3%). Furthermore, the rate of those with a professional qualification certificate was recorded as 83.3%.

Finally, the majority of employees (87.9%) stated that they were provided with personal protective equipment (PPE) when starting work. Some factors occupational experience, ability to use work equipment, participation in OHS training and having a professional qualification certificate, the use of technological equipment that reduces labor-intensive work and heavy workload and etc. in positive OSH practices may be cited as factors that increase productivity and work performance at construction sites

Descriptive statistics were used to reveal the mean and standard deviation values of the survey form statements. Respondents used a 7-point Likert scale to answer the statements. The scale showed strong internal consistency with a Cronbach's Alpha coefficient of 0.97 after reliability analysis. Descriptive statistics for the scale and sub-dimensions of the survey form are presented in Table 3. The satisfaction level of the employees was determined to be 3.50 ± 1.65 , indicating partial dissatisfaction. The employees' perception of responsibility was found to be 5.23 ± 1.98 , indicating a partial perception of responsibility. The employees' perception of obligation was determined to be 4.26 ± 2.47 . The OHS educational status of employees was found to be 5.32 ± 1.53 , indicating a high level of OHS education status. This result shows that OHS training provided to employees will prevent the occurrence of work accidents and occupational diseases by preventing employees from acting unsafely, as well as preventing the occurrence of employee-related unsafe situations on construction sites. Employees' perceptions of OHS (5.10 ± 1.23) and their views on managers' OHS responsibilities (5.12 ± 1.86) are relatively high. However, the employees' views regarding the occupational

safety expert's OHS practices (4.26 ± 1.40) and the site manager's OHS attitudes (3.73 ± 2.11) were at a moderate level. Managers' fulfilment of their OHS responsibilities, reasonable OHS attitudes of construction site managers, and positive OHS practices of occupational safety experts may ensure the creation of a safety culture at construction sites. Moreover, this safety culture created at construction sites will also support the creation of a positive OHS perception among construction site employees.

Table 3. Descriptive statistics

	Mean	Standard deviation	Classification*	Minimum	Maximum
Satisfaction level of employees	3.50	1.65	Slightly less	2.72	3.57
Employees' perception of responsibility	5.23	1.98	Partially high	4.44	5.29
Employees' perception of obligation	4.26	2.47	Medium	3.58	4.43
OHS educational status of employees	5.32	1.53	High	5.30	6.14
OHS perceptions of employees	5.10	1.23	Partially high	4.44	5.29
Employees' views on OHS responsibilities of managers	5.12	1.86	Partially high	4.44	5.29
Employees' views on OHS practices of occupational safety experts	4.26	1.40	Medium	3.58	4.43
Employees' views on OHS attitude of construction site managers	3.73	2.11	Medium	3.58	4.43

Legend: *The interpretation of the descriptive statistics (mean \pm sd) was categorized as follows: 1.00 - 1.86 as at least, 1.87 - 2.71 as less, 2.72-3.57 as slightly less, 3.58-4.43 as medium level, 4.44 - 5.29 as partially high, 5.30 - 6.14 as high, and 6.15 - 7.00 as too high.

4.2. Correlation Analysis

The Spearman correlation analysis was conducted to determine the relationship between employees' age, occupational experience, and daily working time, and their views on OHS practices. Figure 3 shows that there were significant positive relationships between the employees' age and their satisfaction levels ($r = 0.365$; $p < 0.01$), responsibility perceptions ($r = 0.329$; $p < 0.01$), obligation perceptions ($r = 0.273$; $p < 0.01$), OHS training statuses ($r = 0.282$; $p < 0.01$), OHS perceptions ($r = 0.366$; $p < 0.01$), employees' views on OHS responsibilities of managers ($r = 0.221$; $p < 0.05$), and employees' views on OHS practices of occupational safety experts ($r = 0.227$; $p < 0.01$). However, there was no significant relationship between the employees' age and employees' views on OHS attitudes of the site managers.

In the socio-demographic results section of the empirical study, the average age of the employees was recorded as 33.9 ± 9.3 years. This result also showed that construction site employees consist of young adult employees rather than elderly, young and child employees, who are in special risk groups in working life. Based on the results regarding the age of the employees, the following evaluations can be made for correlation analysis: The study showed that the satisfaction levels of young adult employees were high in construction sites that were described with expressions such as poor working conditions and heavy workload, as well as being classified as a very dangerous industry. Young adult employees are more sensitive to OHS training and have a higher perception of responsibility. In addition, they expressed positive views about the managers and safety experts who fulfill their OHS responsibilities at construction sites. However, the views of young adult employees regarding the OHS attitudes of the construction site managers were not positive.

Figure 3: Representation of relationships obtained between variables using Spearman correlation

Legend: Type of Relationships between employees' age (EA), occupational experience (OE), and daily working time (DWT), and their views on OHS practices. (OHS practices; satisfaction level (SL), responsibility perception (RP), obligation perception (OP), OHS training status (TOHS), OHS perception (OHSP), employees' views on OHS responsibilities of managers (R-M), employees' views on OHS practices of occupational safety experts (P-OSE), and employees' views on OHS attitudes of construction site managers (A-CSM)).

Furthermore, the analysis revealed a strong negative correlation between daily working time of employees and their satisfaction levels ($r = - 0.348$; $p < 0.01$), obligation perceptions ($r = - 0.327$; $p < 0.01$), OHS education statuses ($r = - 0.320$; $p < 0.01$), OHS perceptions ($r = - 0.436$; $p < 0.01$), and employees' views on OHS responsibilities of managers ($r = - 0.534$; $p < 0.01$). However, there was no significant correlation between daily working time of the employees and their responsibility perceptions, employees' views on OHS practices of occupational safety experts, and employees' views on OHS attitudes of the site managers. The current research study revealed that the average daily working time of 8.7 ± 1.1 hours for construction site employees creates negative views among employees towards managers and occupational safety experts. This negative view also obscured establishing relationships with employees about their OHS practices such as satisfaction level, perception of responsibility, perception of obligation, OHS education status, OHS perceptions of employees, and views of the employees regarding the site manager's OHS attitudes.

Additionally, in the study was not found significant relationship between the occupational experience of employees and their satisfaction levels, responsibility perceptions, obligation perceptions, OHS education statuses, OHS perceptions, and employees' views on OHS responsibilities of managers. However, there was a significant negative relationship between the occupational experience period of the employees and employees' views on OHS practices of occupational safety experts ($r = - 0.245$; $p < 0.01$) and employees' views on OHS attitudes of the site managers ($r = - 0.209$; $p < 0.05$). The average occupational experience of the employees was determined as 11.2 ± 6.4 years, which represented the occupational experience period of the employees who were at the beginning stage of their working lives. Therefore, the study showed that factors such as perception of OHS, satisfaction level, perception of obligation, and OHS training status of construction site employees who are still at the beginning stage in terms of their

occupational experience can be negatively affected. The study revealed that the high occupational experience of the construction site employees did not concern the managers very much, and also supported the idea that "I am interested in the completion of the job", which is prevalent among the managers.

4.4. Mann-Whitney U (MWU) Tests

The Mann-Whitney U analyzes were performed to reveal the significance levels of the relationships between socio-demographic and occupational characteristics and OHS views of employees (Figure 4a-h). The analysis showed that there were no significant differences between employees' marital status and their satisfaction levels, responsibility perceptions, obligation perceptions, OHS education status), OHS perceptions, employee views on managers' OHS responsibilities, and employee views on occupational safety experts' OHS practices. However, Figure 4(a) showed that there was a significant difference between the employees' views on the OHS attitudes of the construction site managers and their marital status with single employees' views on the OHS attitudes of construction site managers were more positive (MWU = 1356.000; $p < 0.05$). The study revealed that the marital status of employees has no impact on their satisfaction levels, OHS training status, responsibility, obligation, and OHS perceptions, employee views about managers' OHS responsibilities and employee views about occupational safety experts' OHS practices. The research showed that single employees particularly appreciated the OHS attitudes of the construction site manager.

Figure 4(b) shows significant statistical differences between the monthly incomes of employees and their satisfaction levels (MWU = 1322.000; $p < 0.05$), responsibility perception (MWU = 1672.000; $p < 0.05$), and obligation perception (MWU = 1632.000; $p < 0.05$). There are also significant differences in OHS educational status (MWU = 1352.000; $p < 0.05$), OHS perception (MWU = 1458.000; $p < 0.05$), and employee views on managers' OHS responsibility (MWU = 1418.000; $p < 0.05$). The results of the study revealed that construction site employees, particularly those earning \$800 or more per month, had higher levels of satisfaction, a positive perception of OSH, a reasonable perception of responsibility and obligation, a successful OHS training status, and a more positive view of managers' OSH responsibilities. However, there is no significant statistical difference between the monthly income of employees and their views on occupational safety experts' OHS practices, as well as their views on OHS attitudes of construction site managers'.

Figure 4(c) shows that the study found significant differences between job satisfaction of construction site employees and their views on OHS practices, including responsibility perceptions (MWU = 1088.000; $p < 0.05$), satisfaction levels (MWU = 816.000; $p < 0.05$), OHS training situations (MWU = 858.000; $p < 0.05$), OHS perceptions (MWU = 754.000; $p < 0.05$), employee views on the OHS responsibilities of managers (MWU = 644.000, $p < 0.05$), and employee views on the OHS practices of the occupational safety expert (MWU = 1032.000; $p < 0.05$). Employees who were satisfied with their jobs at construction sites were more inclined to perform their OSH obligations compared to dissatisfied employees. They also showed greater motivation to carry out their OHS responsibilities and had a better perception of OHS. Additionally, satisfied employees placed value on OHS training and implemented it. Moreover, managers in construction site settings were more conscientious in meeting their OHS responsibilities. The positive OHS practices of occupational safety experts at construction sites and the recognition of

employees for their work were essential for high satisfaction. There was no significant statistical difference found between the job satisfaction of employees and their views on the OHS attitudes of construction site manager and employees' perception obligation.

As seen in Figure 4(d), the results showed a significant statistical difference between sleepover situations at the workplace of employees and their satisfaction levels, with higher satisfaction among those who do not have to stay at the workplace (MWU = 1366.000, $p < 0.05$). Additionally, there is a significant statistical difference between the sleepover situations at the workplace of employees and their perceptions of responsibility (MWU = 1100.000, $p < 0.05$) and obligation (MWU = 1484.000, $p < 0.05$), with higher levels of responsibility and obligation among those who do not have to sleepover at the workplace. Furthermore, there is a significant statistical difference between sleepover situations at the workplace of employees and their OHS training status. It was revealed that construction site employees with good OHS training generally do not prefer to sleepover at the workplace (MWU = 1170.000; $p < 0.05$).

Similarly, there is a significant statistical difference between the sleepover situations at the workplace of employees and their OHS perceptions, with more positive OHS perceptions among those who do not have to stay at the workplace (MWU = 994.000; $p < 0.05$). Moreover, there is a significant statistical difference between the sleepover situations at the workplace of employees and their views on OHS responsibilities of managers (MWU = 1062.000; $p < 0.05$). Those who did not sleepover at the construction site stated that managers' perception of responsibility was more positive. Additionally, there is a significant statistical difference between the sleepover situations at the workplace of employees and their views on OHS practices of occupational safety experts, with more positive views among those who do not have to stay over (MWU = 1632.000; $p < 0.05$). Finally, it was determined that there was no significant statistical difference between the sleepover situations at the workplace of employees and their views on OHS attitudes of construction site managers.

Figure 4(e) shows test results for significant differences between whether construction site employees' occupations require working at heights and their views on OHS practices. The analysis showed that there were significant differences in the perceptions of responsibility (MWU = 978.000; $p < 0.05$), OHS training situations (MWU = 1156.000; $p < 0.05$), OHS perceptions (MWU = 1116.000; $p < 0.05$), and views on OHS responsibilities of managers (MWU = 1116.000; $p < 0.05$) among construction site employees whose jobs require working at height. These significant differences resulted in construction site employees who work at heights as part of their occupation felt a greater sense of responsibility. They prioritized OHS training and expected managers to perform their OHS responsibilities more effectively as well as had a more positive perception of OHS. However, there was no significant statistical difference in the views of construction site employees on OHS practices of occupational safety experts, their satisfaction levels, their obligation perceptions, and their views on OHS attitudes of the construction site managers based on whether the occupation requires working at heights.

Figure 4: Representation of relationships obtained between variables using MWU

Legend: According to Mann-Whitney U (MWU) test, importance levels of relationships between employees' views on OHS practices and their marital status (MS) (a), monthly income (MI) (b), job satisfaction (JS) (c), sleepovers at workplace (SW) (d), working at heights status (WH) (e), had professional qualification certificate (PQC) (f), received training on working at heights (TWH) (g), and received training on OHS (TOHS) (h). (Employees' views on OHS practices: satisfaction levels (SL), responsibility perceptions (RP), obligation perceptions (OP), OHS perceptions (OHSP), OHS training status (OHSTS), employee views on OHS responsibilities of managers (R-M), employee views on OHS practices of occupational safety experts (P-OSE), and employee views on OHS attitudes of construction site managers (A-CSM).

The results of the MWU analysis in Figure 4(f) revealed a significant difference between employees with a professional qualification certificate and their satisfaction levels (MWU = 842.000; $p < 0.05$), perceptions of responsibility (MWU = 856.000; $p < 0.05$), and views on the OHS attitudes of the construction site managers (MWU = 818.000; $p < 0.05$). The significant differences showed that employees with a professional qualification certificate had high satisfaction levels and perceived responsibility, as well as reasonable views on the OHS attitudes of construction site managers. However, no significant difference was found in the views of employees with a professional qualification certificate and their perception of obligation, their OHS training status, OHS perceptions, views on OHS responsibility of managers and the views on OHS practices of occupational safety experts.

Figure 4(g) presents the test results for the significant difference between the views of employees with training for working at height and their satisfaction levels (MWU = 1358.000; $p < 0.05$), perceptions of responsibility (MWU = 1550.000; $p < 0.05$), OHS training situations (MWU = 1512.000; $p < 0.05$), and OHS perceptions (MWU = 1332.000; $p < 0.05$) and views on OHS responsibilities of managers (MWU = 1338.000; $p < 0.05$). The study revealed that employees who received training on working at height showed higher satisfaction levels, a more developed sense of responsibility, and positive views on OHS training and manager responsibilities. However, there was no significant difference between the views of employees with training for working at height and their obligation perceptions, views on OHS practices of the occupational safety experts and views on OHS attitudes of the construction site manager. The MWU analysis revealed significant differences between the views of employees regarding the status of receiving OHS training when starting work and their satisfaction levels (MWU = 516.000; $p < 0.05$), responsibility perceptions (MWU = 478.000; $p < 0.05$), obligation perceptions (MWU = 786.000; $p < 0.05$), OHS training statuses (MWU = 662.000; $p < 0.05$), OHS perceptions (MWU = 460.000; $p < 0.05$), views on OHS responsibilities of managers (MWU = 584.000; $p < 0.05$) and views on OHS practices of the occupational safety experts (MWU = 952.000; $p < 0.05$), except for views on OHS attitudes of the construction site managers. Providing OHS training to employees at the beginning of their employment enhanced their satisfaction, sense of responsibility, and positive attitude towards safety obligations. It also improved their OHS training status and reinforced their belief that managers and safety experts fulfilled their OHS responsibilities effectively (Figure 4h).

4.5. Kruskal-Wallis H Tests

Figure 5 presents the results of the Kruskal-Wallis H test between the occupations of employees and their views on OHS practices. The analysis revealed a significant difference in satisfaction levels among employees based on occupation, with bricklayers reporting higher satisfaction (KWH = 24.145; $p < 0.05$). Additionally, there were significant differences in their perceptions of responsibility (KWH = 48.255; $p < 0.05$) and obligation (KWH = 32.109; $p < 0.05$) based on occupation, with bricklayers showing a higher perception of these factors. Furthermore, there was a significant difference in views about their OHS training statuses based on occupation, with bricklayers holding more positive views (KWH = 49.124; $p < 0.05$). The analysis also found a significant difference in their OHS perceptions based on occupation, with bricklayers holding more positive views (KWH = 47.930; $p < 0.05$). Similarly, there was a significant difference in views on OHS responsibilities of managers based on occupation, with bricklayers having more positive

views (KWH = 42.211; $p < 0.05$). However, there was no significant difference in views on OHS practices of the occupational safety experts based on occupation. Finally, there was a significant difference in views on OHS attitudes of the construction site manager based on occupation, with those in other occupations holding more positive views (KWH = 11.809; $p < 0.05$).

Figure 5: Representation of relationships obtained between variables using KWH

Legend: According to Kruskal-Wallis H (KWH) test, importance levels of relationships between employees' occupations (bricklayer (B), Plasterer (P), ironmaster (I), moulder (M), and others (O)) and their views on OHS practices (satisfaction level (SL), responsibility perception (RP), obligation perception (OP), OHS training status (OHSTS), OHS perception (OHSP), employee views on OHS responsibilities of managers (R-M), employee views on OHS practices of occupational safety experts (P-OSE), and employee views on OHS attitudes of construction site managers (A-CSM).

Figure 6 displays the test results for significant differences between the education levels of construction site employees and their views on OHS practices. The analysis revealed no significant statistical difference between education level of construction site employees and their satisfaction levels, responsibility perceptions, and obligation perceptions. Still, there was a significant statistical difference between their education level and OHS training statuses, with high school graduates holding more positive views (KWH = 14.703; $p < 0.05$). Additionally, there were no significant statistical differences between their education level and views on OHS responsibilities of managers, views on OHS practices of occupational safety experts, OHS perceptions, and views on OHS attitudes of construction site managers.

Figure 6: Representation of relationships obtained between variables using KWH

Legend: According to Kruskal-Wallis H (KWH) test, importance levels of relationships between employees' education levels (illiterate (I), primary education (5 years) (P5), primary school (8 years) (P8), high school (H) and bachelor's degree (B)) and their views on OHS practices (satisfaction level (SL), responsibility perception (RP), obligation perception (OP), OHS training status (OHSTS), OHS perception (OHSP), employee views on OHS responsibilities of managers (R-M), employee views on OHS practices of occupational safety experts (P-OSE), and employee views on OHS attitudes of construction site managers (A-CSM).

4.6. Multiple Comparison Tests Based on Occupation and Education Level

As shown in Table 4, the results of the multiple comparison test indicate significant statistical differences ($p < 0.05$) between the occupation of employees and their views on OHS practices. There are significant statistical differences in satisfaction levels among employees in the bricklaying occupation compared to those in the moulder and ironmaster occupations, as well as among employees in other occupational groups compared to those in the moulder and ironmaster occupations. Employees' perception of responsibility varies significantly among construction site employees in the moulder occupation compared to those in the bricklaying, plasterer, and other occupational groups.

Table 4. Multiple comparison test between occupations of construction site employees and their views on OHS practices

OHS views	Occupations		Mean difference	Significance (p-value)
Satisfaction level	Bricklayer	Moulder	1.758*	0.001
		Ironmaster	1.891*	0.001
	Others	Moulder	1.296*	0.021
Responsibility perception	Moulder	Ironmaster	1.429*	0.028
		Bricklayer	-2.620*	0.000
		Plasterer	-1.908*	0.000
	Ironmaster	Others	-1.782*	0.002
		Bricklayer	-2.646*	0.000
Obligation perception	Bricklayer	Plasterer	-1933*	0.002
		Others	-1.808*	0.009
		Moulder	3.537*	0.000
		Ironmaster	3.292*	0.000
OHS education status	Bricklayer	Plasterer	2.300*	0.017
		Others	2.706*	0.005
		Moulder	2.358*	0.000
	Plaster	Ironmaster	1.781*	0.000
		Moulder	1.807*	0.000
OHS perception	Others	Ironmaster	1.230*	0.014
		Moulder	1.505*	0.000
		Bricklayer	-1.927*	0.000
	Moulder	Plasterer	-1.366*	0.000
		Others	-1.209*	0.000
		Bricklayer	-1.443*	0.000
Views on OHS responsibilities of managers	Ironmaster	Plasterer	-0.882*	0.038
		Bricklayer	-2.564*	0.000
		Plasterer	-1.841*	0.000
	Moulder	Others	-1.682*	0.002
		Bricklayer	-2.386*	0.000
		Plasterer	-1.662*	0.007
Views on OHS attitudes of construction site managers	Bricklayer	Others	-1.504*	0.028
		Ironmaster	-1.873*	0.035
		Others	-2.353*	0.009

*The mean difference is significant at the 0.05 level

Similarly, there are significant differences in the perception of responsibility among construction site employees in ironsmith occupation compared to those in the bricklaying, plasterer, and other occupational groups. Significant differences in terms of obligation exist among employees in the bricklaying occupation compared to those in moulder, plasterer, and other occupational groups. OHS training statuses also show significant differences among employees in the bricklaying occupation compared to those in moulder and ironsmith occupations. Similarly, there are significant statistical differences in OHS training statuses between employees in plasterer and moulder occupations, as well as employees in the bricklaying occupation and other occupational groups. OHS perception varies

significantly among employees in the moulder occupation compared to those in the bricklaying, plasterer, and other occupational groups. Similarly, there are significant differences in the OHS perception among employees in ironsmith occupations compared to those in the bricklaying and plasterer occupations. Views on OHS responsibilities of managers also differ significantly among employees in the moulder occupation compared to those in the bricklaying, plasterer, and other occupational groups. Similarly, there are significant differences in the views on OHS responsibilities of managers among employees in ironsmith occupations compared to those in the bricklaying, plasterer, and other occupational groups.

5. Conclusions and Recommendations

The study was designed to reveal the practice level of OHS measures at construction sites. To determine how socio-demographic and occupational characteristics influence views on OHS practices, we applied correlation analysis. This clarified the significance levels of these relationships. The socio-demographic and occupational characteristics of construction site employees have an impact on their views on OHS practices, both positively and negatively. Most construction site employees surveyed were married and had an average of 11 years of occupational experience. Adult and young construction site employees were found to be satisfied with working on construction sites despite heavy workloads, difficult working conditions, and numerous unsafe situations. These findings were consistent with studies showing a negative relationship between aging and OHS, which investigated the impact of aging on the physical strength of construction site employees and OHS (Lunde et al., 2014; Peng & Chan, 2019). Additionally, Laberge and Ledoux (2011) suggested in their study that young employees' OHS factors, including demographic, individual, professional, organizational, temporal, and operational factors, should be examined in both qualitative and quantitative studies. Kecojević et al. (2007) analyzed the relationship between work-related fatalities and occupational experience, finding that 44% of employees who died in equipment-related incidents had less than five years of occupational experience. Furthermore, a meta-analysis conducted between 1998 and 2018 found a positive relationship between health issues (depression, diabetes, hypertension, cardiovascular and cerebrovascular diseases) and long working hours (Wong et al., 2019).

Furthermore, construction sites with poor working conditions and safety hazards can enhance young adult construction employees' sense of responsibility, leading to increased compliance with work obligations and a strong commitment to OHS practices. A longitudinal study conducted on firefighters in the United Arab Emirates revealed a direct link between OHS practices, improved workplace environment, increased employee productivity, and enhanced OHS practices. The study also noted a significant change in employees' OHS perception, leading to improved productivity (Lari, 2024).

On the other hand, it has been shown that the average workday of construction site employees, nearly 9 hours a day, leads to negative views of managers regarding OHS responsibilities, as well as negative outcomes such as: (I) Decrease in satisfaction levels (II) not fulfilling obligations (III) not participating in OHS practices and training. Marital status did not significantly impact employees' views on OHS practices, but factors such as monthly income, workplace sleepovers, job satisfaction, OHS training, and working at height training did have a significant impact on their OHS practices. Analysis revealed that bricklayers and high school graduates reported more positive views on OHS practices,

suggesting educational and occupational influences on safety perceptions. In their study, Cao et al. (2021) showed that effective OHS training was positively related to job responsibilities, OHS training, and job satisfaction. Similarly, they revealed that it was significantly related to the employment certificate, duration of education, training method, and working time, but not related to the person's age, marital status, education level, type of job, or whether they had a work accident.

It is evident that the employees are only partially satisfied, indicating a need for further improvement in working conditions to boost overall satisfaction levels. To achieve this, it is essential to create social facilities where employees can engage in social activities outside of working hours. Additionally, dormitory rooms should be regularly cleaned, and an adequate number of showers and WCs should be provided. Improving the quality and quantity of food will also contribute to increased employee productivity. Employers should also consider providing transportation for employees to construction sites or workplaces. Ultimately, it is important to recognize that individuals with higher satisfaction levels are more likely to take ownership of their work and demonstrate greater efficiency.

Funding declaration: This research received no specific grant from any funding agency in the public, commercial, or not-for-profit sectors.

Conflict of interest: The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest.

References

- Abdelhamid, T. S., & Everett, J. G. (2000). Identifying root causes of construction accidents. *Journal of Construction Engineering and Management*, 126(1), 52-60. Doi: [https://doi.org/10.1061/\(ASCE\)0733-9364\(2000\)126:1\(52\)](https://doi.org/10.1061/(ASCE)0733-9364(2000)126:1(52))
- Ajzen, I. (1991). The theory of planned behavior. *Organizational Behavior and Human Decision Processes*, 50(2), 179-211. Doi: [https://doi.org/10.1016/0749-5978\(91\)90020-t](https://doi.org/10.1016/0749-5978(91)90020-t)
- Amegayibor, G. K. (2021). The effect of demographic factors on employees' performance: a case of an owner-manager manufacturing firm. *Annals of Human Resource Management Research*, 1(2), 127-143. Doi: <https://doi.org/10.35912/ahrmr.v1i2.853>.
- Bird, F. (1974). *Management guide to loss control*. Institute Press, Atlanta, GA.
- Cao, Z., Chen, T., & Cao, Y. (2021). Effect of occupational health and safety training for Chinese construction workers based on the CHAID decision tree. *Frontiers in Public Health*, 9, 623441, 1-10. Doi: <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpubh.2021.623441>.
- Chua, D. K. H., & Goh, Y. M. (2004). Incident causation model for improving feedback of safety knowledge. *Journal of Construction Engineering and Management*, 130(4), 542-551. Doi: [https://doi.org/10.1061/\(ASCE\)0733-9364\(2004\)130:4\(542\)](https://doi.org/10.1061/(ASCE)0733-9364(2004)130:4(542))
- Çalışkan, H., & Kılınc, G. (2012). The relationship between the learning styles of students and their attitudes towards social studies course. *Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 55, 47-56. Doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2012.09.476>
- De Barros, M. D., De Freitas, J. G., Costa, H. G., Gutierrez, R. H., & De Souza, C.G. (2018). The choosing of teaching methods according to entrepreneurial profiles: a multicriteria approach. *International Journal of Engineering Education*, 34(1), 217-225.
- Demirkesen, S., & Arditi, D. (2015). Construction safety personnel's perceptions of safety training practices. *International Journal of Project Management*, 33(5), 1160-1169. Doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijproman.2015.01.007>

- Dong, X. S., Wang, X. & Largay, J.A. (2015). Occupational and non-occupational factors associated with work-related injuries among construction workers in the USA. *International Journal of Occupational and Environmental Health*, 21(2), 142-150. Doi: 10.1179/2049396714Y.0000000107
- Duan, P., & Zhou, J. (2023). Cascading vulnerability analysis of unsafe behaviors of construction workers from the perspective of network modeling. *Engineering, Construction and Architectural Management*, 30(3), 1037-1060. Doi: <https://doi.org/10.1108/ECAM-06-2021-0475>
- Edwards, J. R. D., Davey, J., & Armstrong, K. (2013). Returning to the roots of culture: A review and re-conceptualisation of safety culture. *Safety Science*, 55, 70-80. Doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ssci.2013.01.004>
- Fang, D., Huang, Y., Guo, H., & Lim, H. W. (2020). LCB approach for construction safety. *Safety Science*, 128, 104761. Doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ssci.2020.104761>
- Fang, D., & Wu, H. 2013. Development of a safety culture interaction (SCI) model for construction projects. *Safety Science*, 57, 138-149. Doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ssci.2013.02.003>.
- Flegl, M., Depoo, L., & Alcazar, M. (2022). The impact of employees' training on their performance improvements. *Quality Innovation Prosperity*, 26(1), 70-89. Doi: <https://doi.org/10.12776/qip.v26i1.1665>
- Garrett, J.W., & Teizer, J. (2009). Human factors analysis classification system relating to human error awareness taxonomy in construction safety. *Journal of Construction Engineering and Management*, 135, 754-763. Doi: [https://doi.org/10.1061/\(ASCE\)CO.1943-7862.0000034](https://doi.org/10.1061/(ASCE)CO.1943-7862.0000034)
- Goetz, K., Musselmann, B., Szecsenyi, J., & Joos, S. (2013). The influence of workload and health behavior on job satisfaction of general practitioners. *Family Medicine*, 45(2), 95-101.
- Guldenmund, F. (2010). (Mis)understanding safety culture and its relationship to safety management. *Risk Analysis: An International Journal*, 30(10), 1466-1480. Doi: <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1539-6924.2010.01452.x>
- Heinrich, H. W. (1969). *Industrial accident prevention*, 4th ed. McGraw-Hill, New York.
- Heinrich, H. W. (1980). *Industrial accident prevention*. McGraw-Hil, New York.
- Jaafar, M. H., Arifin, K., Aiyub, K., Razman, M. R., Ishak, M. I. S., & Samsurijan, M. S. (2018). Occupational safety and health management in the construction industry: A review. *International Journal of Occupational Safety and Ergonomics*, 24, 493–506. Doi: <https://doi.org/10.1080/10803548.2017.1366129>
- Jafari, M. J., Barkhordari, A., Eskandari, D., & Mehrabi, Y. (2019). Relationships between certain individual characteristics and occupational accidents. *International Journal of Occupational Safety and Ergonomics*, 25(1), 61-65. Doi: <https://doi.org/10.1080/10803548.2018.1502232>
- Kecojevic, V., Komljenovic, D., Groves, W., & Radomsky, M. (2007). An analysis of equipment-related fatal accidents in US mining operations: 1995–2005. *Safety Science*, 45(8), 864-874. Doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ssci.2006.08.024>
- Kerr, W. (1957). Complementary theories of safety psychology. *The Journal of Social Psychology*, 45, 3-9. Doi: <https://doi.org/10.1080/00224545.1957.9714280>.
- Kikuchi, H., Odagiri, Y., Ohya, Y., Nakanishi, Y., Shimomitsu, T., Theorell, T. & Inoue, S. (2020) Association of overtime work hours with various stress responses in 59,021 Japanese workers: retrospective cross-sectional study. *PLoS One*, 15(3), e0229506. Doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0229506
- Laberge, M., & Ledoux, E. (2011). Occupational health and safety issues affecting young workers: A literature review. *Work*, 39(3), 215-232. Doi:10.3233/WOR-2011-1170.
- Lari, M. (2024). A longitudinal study on the impact of occupational health and safety practices on employee productivity. *Safety Science*, 170, 106374. Doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ssci.2023.106374>

- Li, H., Lu, M., Hsu, S.C., Gray, M., & Huang, T. (2015). Proactive behavior-based safety management for construction safety improvement. *Safety Science*, 75, 107-117. Doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ssci.2015.01.013>
- Lunde, L. K., Koch, M., Knardahl, S., Wærsted, M., Mathiassen, S. E., Forsman, M., & Veiersted, K. B. (2014). Musculoskeletal health and work ability in physically demanding occupations: study protocol for a prospective field study on construction and health care workers. *BMC Public Health*, 14, 1-11. Doi: <https://doi.org/10.1186/1471-2458-14-1075>
- Mitropoulos, P., Abdelhamid, T. S., & Howell, G. A. (2005). Systems model of construction accident causation. *Journal of Construction Engineering and Management*, 131(7), 816-825. Doi: [https://doi.org/10.1061/\(ASCE\)0733-9364\(2005\)131:7\(816\)](https://doi.org/10.1061/(ASCE)0733-9364(2005)131:7(816))
- OSHA (2018). Inspection: 1325061.015 - Rj Drew Construction Services Inc., available at: www.osha.gov/ords/imis/establishment.inspection_detail?id¼1325061.015 (accessed 20 November 2023).
- Peng, L., & Chan, A. H. (2019). A meta-analysis of the relationship between ageing and occupational safety and health. *Safety Science*, 112, 162-172. Doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ssci.2018.10.030>
- Petersen, D., (1971). *Techniques of Safety Management*. McGraw-Hil, New York.
- Reason, J. (2000). Human error: Models and management. *Western Journal of Medicine*, 12, 393–396. Doi: 10.1136/ewjm.172.6.393
- Shappell, S. A., & Wiegmann, D. A. (1997). A human error approach to accident investigation: The taxonomy of unsafe operations. *The International Journal of Aviation Psychology*, 7, 269–291. Doi: https://doi.org/10.1207/s15327108ijap0704_2
- Silbey, S. S. (2009). Taming Prometheus: Talk about safety and culture. *Annual Review of Sociology*, 35(1), 341-369. Doi: <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev.soc.34.040507.134707>
- Song, Y., & Zhao, X. (2021). Normality testing of high-dimensional data based on principle component and Jarque–Bera statistics. *Stats*, 4(1), 216-227. Doi: <https://doi.org/10.3390/stats4010016>
- Suraji, A., Duff, A. R., & Peckitt, S. J. (2001). Development of causal model of construction accident causation. *Journal of Construction Engineering and Management*, 127, 337. Doi: [https://doi.org/10.1061/\(ASCE\)0733-9364\(2001\)1274\(337\)](https://doi.org/10.1061/(ASCE)0733-9364(2001)1274(337))
- Vitharana, V., De Silva, G., & De Silva, S. (2015). Health hazards, risk and safety practices in construction sites - A review study. *Engineer*, 48(3), 35-44. Doi: 10.4038/engineer.v48i3.6840
- Wang, J., Zou, P. X. W., & Li, P. P. (2016). Critical Factors and paths influencing construction workers' safety risk tolerances. *Accident Analysis & Prevention*, 93, 267-279. Doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aap.2015.11.027>
- Wong, K., Chan, A. H., & Ngan, S. C. (2019). The effect of long working hours and overtime on occupational health: a meta-analysis of evidence from 1998 to 2018. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 16(12), 2102-2014. Doi: 10.3390/ijerph16122102
- Yi, W., & Chan, A. (2016). Health profile of construction workers in Hong Kong. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 13(12), 1232-1247. Doi: <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph1312123>
- Zohar, D., & Luria, G. (2005). A multilevel model of safety climate: cross-level relationships between organization and group-level climates. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 90(4), 616-628. Doi: <https://doi.org/10.1037/0021-9010.90.4.616>